

1 Mapping Architectural Comparanda: AI Methods for Large Scale Analysis of the Archaeological Record for Reconstruction of Greco-Roman Architecture

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Abstract

We present a multi-stage pipeline for collecting, filtering, and structuring literature on Greco-Roman temples and libraries. The workflow spans (i) large-scale retrieval using author-name and keyword queries, (ii) initial relevancy scoring with a visual-language model (Colpali), (iii) supervised classifiers operating on titles and on sequences of detected figures/tables, and (iv) information extraction to produce building-level metadata (order, typology, chronology, location) with evidence snippets. We conclude with an interactive web map visualizing aggregated site/building data.

Keywords: Greco-Roman architecture, Libraries, Temples, Information extraction, Document classification

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1. Introduction

Among the archaeological data generated from excavations, building remains and architectural materials are of the largest scale and the most complicated to understand and reconstruct. The mission of archaeology is to document their state of preservation in drawings, text and numerical measurements, analyze them, deduce their initial form, and interpret them in terms of processes, associations that led to them the way they are. The challenge is that data are always partial and fragmentary to various degrees. To reconstruct a building, archaeologists must identify the known (invariable) parts of the building, and using geographical, chronological, typological, or stylistic criteria identify among the whole archaeological record, other parallel and precedent comparable designs (architectural comparanda), based on which they can infer the missing (variable) parts. This process is very laborious and never conclusive, due to inconsistency in the state of preservation, the level of detail or the format of the publications. Moreover, the interpretive framework and available evidence change over time in the history of scholarship. Often there are more possible hypotheses. To systematize this effort, archaeologists may create taxonomies for the classification of artifacts and use statistical analysis, however, the use of these methods is still very limited.

Our project is grounded in the applicability and transferability of this methodology in development of methods for using generative AI that has the unprecedented capacity to analyze vast amounts of archaeological records at scale, and create a dataset of buildings annotated with their architectural principles and linked to their “comparanda” based on a variety of criteria. Among the different styles, GrecoRoman architecture is an excellent case study for the development of AI-based methods, because it consists of a certain vocabulary of architectural components related with certain relationships, proportions and sequences. A major challenge is the highly variable nature of the archaeological data, such as textual descriptions, measurements, and drawings. Manually analyzing such records at scale is not practical for experts.

In this work, our goal is to develop natural language processing (NLP) and generative AI techniques and language models to parse this unstructured and diverse data, extract the relationships between the various buildings directly from the images of the archaeological records, analyze this data at scale, synthesize and visualize it in a network of buildings (network nodes) linked to their “comparanda” based on various criteria (links), and expand this network via statistical inference. We believe that this network and compilation will assist archaeologists in the identification of parallels (architectural comparanda) for any building they might be analyzing while also compiling a bibliography with all available primary and secondary sources. Moreover, the work described in this manuscript will form the basis for deeper analysis by AI methods that focus on process the compiled textual material more richly and apply various analytical methods including statistical analysis, topological analysis, stylistic features, to infer relationships of buildings that are not known in the literary record, e.g. based on ratios, adjacency relationships, certain sequences or motifs in the design that can convey cultural interconnections that can then assist the humanistic inquiry of their interpretation based on the mobility of workshops, trading relationships, internationalization of patrons, etc. Ultimately, the objective of this project is to visualize this analysis and translate the inferred design principles into visual rules that can then be applied to generate accurate and traceable automated reconstructions of architectural plans of archaeological findings.

45 In this work, we computationally curate a collection of heterogeneous architectural records
 46 pertaining to Classical libraries and temples, infer relationships between them, and finally vi-
 47 sualize our rich curated collection via a publicly-browsable interactive map. In the rest of this
 48 document, we describe our methodology in detail that comprises following steps: a) compiling a
 49 vast-coverage collection of classical architectural records, b) developing computational methods
 50 to filter this general collection to focus on classical buildings – specifically libraries and temples,
 51 c) linking the architectural records to individual buildings and populating architectural taxonomy
 52 of the identified buildings, and d) visualizing our compiled taxonomy and collection via an inter-
 53 active map.

54 2. Compiling Vast-Coverage Architectural Record Collection

55 The focus of this stage is to compile a large corpus of architectural records and publications
 56 pertaining to classical architecture. Understandably, this collection is expected to contain a ma-
 57 jority of records that are unrelated to classical buildings, even more so for the targeted case of
 58 libraries and temples. However, this focus on high-coverage from a variety of sources for archae-
 59 ological publications is essential for a comprehensive collection of classical libraries and temples
 60 that is obtained by analysis of a filtered partition of this high-coverage collection. For this initial
 61 collection, we compiled and identified a list of authors of publications on classical archaeological
 62 buildings in an iterative manner. We first extracted a seed list of authors from the bibliographies
 63 of four monographs on temples and libraries and eight general sources/textbooks on ancient
 64 architecture, as well as list of keywords. Later, we expanded on this author list by expanding our
 65 query for searching publication databases via analysis of the results of our seed collection.

66 2.1. Querying Using Author Names Present in Seed Archaeological Publications

67 First of all, to assemble a domain-relevant corpus on Greco-Roman architecture, we started
 68 from four specialist monographs on ancient temples and libraries, two building types within our
 69 own specialization, as well as several general sources and textbooks on ancient classical archi-
 70 tecture. This allowed us to compile a catalog of 674 Author Names. Each name was normal-
 71 ized as a field-restricted author query, and we developed a custom web-scraper that was used
 72 to automate search and compilation across scholarly indexes, prioritizing items indexed on JS-
 73 TOR for their disciplinary coverage and stable, citable records. The scraper issued the queries,
 74 harvested metadata and links for peer-reviewed journal articles and scholarly monographs, and
 75 consolidated the results into a single dataset. This process returned metadata for approximately
 76 27,000 documents associated with the queried authors, which served as the initial corpus for
 77 subsequent screening and analysis.

Table 1 – Summary of Step 1 data collection.

Item	Value
Seed publications (count)	4
Authors extracted (count)	674
Primary source focus	JSTOR (journals, books)
# of entries with metadata (approx.)	27,000

78 2.2. Expanded Query

79 In a second pass, eight additional major publications were mined for author names, yield-
80 ing 794 further unique authors and bringing the author-query set to 1,467. To broaden topical
81 coverage beyond the seed authors, we curated 36 domain-specific keywords spanning classi-
82 cal architectural elements and key archaeological sites. The custom scraper executed both the
83 expanded author queries and the keyword queries across the same scholarly indexes (with em-
84 phasis on JSTOR), collected bibliographic metadata and stable links/DOIs, and appended the
85 results to the working dataset.

86 The expanded crawl produced 99,087 candidate documents in total (including the ~27,000
87 from Step 1), constituting the pre-screening corpus for analysis.

Table 2 – Summary of Step 2 expanded collection.

Item	Value
Additional seed publications (count)	8
Additional authors extracted (count)	794
Total unique authors queried (count)	1,467
Keywords (count)	36
# of documents with metadata	99,087

88 3. Automatic Prediction of Document Relevance to Classical Temples and Libraries

89 In this section, we describe how we use the metadata of the documents above and the full
90 text of a small subset of the documents with permissible licensing, is used to build computational
91 systems for automatically identifying documents and records that pertain to classical architec-
92 ture of ancient libraries and temples. First, we use images and text of a very small subset of
93 documents using a vision-language model called ColPali (Faysse et al., 2024) to generate rele-
94 vance scores for the documents on this subset. These scores are manually analyzed to create a
95 clean training set for building a comparatively lightweight computational system that can esti-
96 mate reliable relevance scores based just on the title from the metadata of the documents. This
97 classifier was used to whittle down the list of potentially relevant documents to a much smaller
98 number compared to the initial set of documents identified above. Finally, we developed a more
99 sophisticated approach to use the visual information in the full versions of this smaller set of doc-
100 uments to train a more reliable relevance predictor that yielded a final compact set of documents
101 that pertain to ancient GrecoRoman libraries and temples.

102 3.1. Using Vision-Language models to create Relevance Training Data via Manual Inspection

103 To prioritize materials for manual screening, we ran an initial relevance pass over a strati-
104 fied subset of 3,000 documents drawn from the aggregated corpus described above. The subset
105 preserved the proportional mix of author-seeded and keyword-seeded items and spanned publi-
106 cation venues and decades to limit source and period bias. Each metadata record was normalized
107 prior to scoring (canonicalized title, deduplicated DOI/URL, and minimal metadata validation).

108 We employed *Colpali* (Faysse et al., 2024), a visual-language model intended for retrieval-
109 augmented workflows, in inference mode to estimate the likelihood that a document contains
110 information pertinent to Greco-Roman temples and libraries. Four short textual queries were

111 authored by domain experts to reflect complementary facets of the topic space (architectural el-
 112 ements, ritual/functional contexts, site-specific case studies, and library-related infrastructures).
 113 For each document–query pair, Colpali produced a scalar compatibility score. Document-level
 114 relevance was then computed as the mean across the four queries,

$$s(d) = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=1}^4 s(q_i, d),$$

115 and the resulting scores were used to rank the small subset of 3,000 documents from highest to
 116 lowest estimated relevance.

117 To assess face validity and surface systematic errors (e.g., homonymous terms, off-topic but
 118 formally similar content), two procedures were followed: (i) expert manual review of the highest-
 119 scoring documents, and (ii) spot checks sampled across the score distribution. Reviewers an-
 120 notated obvious false positives/negatives, flagged problematic metadata (e.g., broken links or
 121 non-scholarly sources that slipped through), and recorded notes for subsequent query/model
 122 adjustments.

123 The evaluation produced a structured table of 3,000 records, comprising a stable document
 124 link, normalized title, four Colpali query scores, and the cross-query average, sorted by the mean
 125 score for expert inspection. This artifact served as the working list for targeted reading and for
 126 refining downstream screening criteria and query formulations.

127 3.2. Document Relevance Classifier Based on Titles

128 From the 3,000 Colpali scored documents, we drew a simple random sample of 300 titles
 129 with stratification across three Colpali score bins so that each bin contributed an equal number
 130 of items. Two scholars independently annotated each title for topical relevance to Greco-Roman
 131 temples and libraries. Disagreements were resolved by discussion, and inter annotator agree-
 132 ment was computed to monitor consistency. The resulting consensus labels served to create
 133 training data for a text classifier that would take document titles as input and predict whether
 134 the documents is relevant to Classical library or temple architecture.

135 Title text was processed in three steps: (i) translation into English through OpenAI’s GPT
 136 application programming interface ¹, (ii) conversion to lower case and lemmatization, and (iii)
 137 augmentation with optional notes and keywords identified by the expert scholars in the first
 138 manual pass over the small list of documents described above, appended as [SEP] tokens. For
 139 example, the French title « *La Stoa de Zeus et la Stoa Royale à l’Agora d’Athènes* » was translated to
 140 “The Stoa of Zeus and the Royal Stoa in the Agora of Athens” and then augmented to [SEP] stoa
 141 [SEP] agora. A RoBERTa-based classifier was trained on the titles dataset processed in the
 142 manner described above. RoBERTa (Liu et al., 2019) is a popular large transformer-based model
 143 pretrained on massive amounts of internet data for producing contextualized representation of
 144 language. Each processed title was encoded with RoBERTa, and the representation was taken
 145 directly from the final layer vector of the special classification token [CLS]. A two class classifier
 146 was trained on the manually annotated data of the 300 titles with a standard cross entropy
 147 objective. The model returned a probability of relevance, and an item was marked relevant when
 148 that probability exceeded a threshold chosen on a validation partition to favor high recall for the
 149 positive class. By construction, the training sample was balanced across the two classes, and no
 150 class weighting was applied.

¹<https://openai.com/api/>

151 **Test Performance.** See Table 3. We prioritize recall for the positive class to minimize false
 152 negatives before subsequent content based filtering. The classifier seems to be reasonably per-
 153 formant at the task of predicting relevance to classical library and temple architecture.

Table 3 – Title-based classifier performance on the test set.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
0 (irrelevant)	0.97	0.86	0.91	43
1 (relevant)	0.74	0.94	0.83	18
Accuracy				0.89

154 Using this title-only classifier on all of the metadata collected in the earlier stages described
 155 above, 29,498 of the 99,087 documents were assigned a positive relevance label (class 1) and
 156 were retained for subsequent content level filtering.

157 3.3. Document Relevance Classifier Based on Sequence of Image and Table Content of the 158 Documents

159 From the 29,498 files labeled as relevant based on title alone, we drew a stratified sample
 160 of 541 documents to automatically assess visual and tabular content of the documents. Each
 161 document was processed with layout parsing to detect the presence of figures and tables. This
 162 screening identified 168 documents with no visual or tabular content and 373 documents with at
 163 least one figure or table. Domain experts on our team noted that relevant archaeological reports
 164 typically include visual materials and tabulated findings; thus confirming that the 168 documents
 165 lacking such content were irrelevant. For the 373 documents that did include visuals or tables,
 166 topical relevance was manually annotated, yielding 228 relevant and 145 irrelevant items. This
 167 small set served as training data for a more refined classifier that paid attention to the number
 168 and order of images and tabular content in the documents.

169 Figures and tables were then detected, cropped, and exported as PNG files. All documents
 170 with no images and tables were discarded. We trained a sequential LSTM (Hochreiter and Schmid-
 171 huber, 1997) model to predict the relevance of the documents based on the ordering and ap-
 172 pearance of images and tables in the documents. For each document, we first computed image
 173 embeddings of extracted images and tables with a pretrained vision encoder called EfficientNet-
 174 B5 (Tan and Le, 2019) and ordered them sequentially according to their appearance in the doc-
 175 ument. A bidirectional LSTM model then processed this sequence of embeddings for a given
 176 document and produced a document level relevance score. Training used the manual relevance
 177 labels from the 373 annotated items identified above, with stratified splits for validation. The
 178 decision threshold was selected to favor high recall for the positive class, consistent with the
 179 upstream screening goals.

180 **Results.** Across the 29,498 title relevant files, only 9,957 contained figures or tables. The
 181 trained sequence-based LSTM classifier was applied to these 9,957 documents. In Taboe 5, we
 182 can see that our classifier reliably identifies the relevant documents based on the high-level
 183 image and table features in the documents. The resulting thresholded outcome is summarized
 184 in Table 6, which provides us with a final estimated list of documents that were actually relevant
 185 to Classical Library/Temple architecture out of the initial 100k documents in our high-coverage
 186 collection of archaeological record metadata.

Table 4 – Counts from layout parsing and manual labeling (sample of 541 documents).

Category	Count
No figures/tables (all irrelevant)	168
With figures and/or tables	373
Relevant (manual)	228
Irrelevant (manual)	145

Table 5 – Sequence-based classifier performance on the test set (documents with figures/tables).

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
0 (irrelevant)	0.90	0.87	0.89	31
1 (relevant)	0.91	0.93	0.92	44
Accuracy	0.91 (75 documents)			
Macro avg	0.91	0.90	0.90	75
Weighted avg	0.91	0.91	0.91	75

Table 6 – Classifier score thresholds on 9,957 documents with figures/tables.

Score threshold	Documents (\geq threshold)
≥ 0.50	3,292
≥ 0.80	2,624
≥ 0.95	1,778

187 4. Building Name Extraction and Taxonomy of Relevant Attributes

188 As described above, we built automatic systems to identify about 2,000 archaeological doc-
189 uments that are likely pertinent to ancient GrecoRoman temples and libraries. In this section, we
190 describe how we automatically linked these records to the actual buildings whose architecture
191 they describe. We used open-weight large language models (Qwen et al., 2025) for this auto-
192 matic linkage. We developed an in-context learning procedure that uses a chain of thought style
193 prompt to extract structured archaeological attributes from prose. To elaborate, we provide the
194 language model with a detailed prompt that describes the task, and contains a worked out ex-
195 ample of the expected output for one of the queries. The prompt guides the model through two
196 sequential stages. The expected output targets surfacing information in the free form document
197 text to populate a manually created archaeological taxonomy by the experts on our team that
198 focuses on order, typology, age, , date etc.

199 **Stage one: entity and evidence location.** For each article, the model identifies the main build-
200 ings discussed in text and locates the paragraphs that describe architectural style, architectural
201 order, period or age, and other attributes of interest. The prompt requests paragraph identifiers
202 and brief evidence snippets for each detected building and attribute.

203 **Stage two: attribute normalization and typing.** From the located paragraphs, the model ex-
204 tracts attribute terms and maps them to an expert-curated taxonomy. Terms for *style* and *order*
205 are selected from a closed vocabulary provided in full within the prompt. For *age* and other at-
206 tributes, the prompt supplies instructive examples without limiting the space of valid outputs,
207 so the model can record free text values when appropriate alongside normalized fields.

208 The prompt is organized to include the following: an instruction block that specifies the task
 209 and output schema, the closed vocabularies for style and order, a compact set of examples for
 210 age and other attributes, and a manually worked example that pairs an example paragraph with
 211 the expected extraction. The model returns one structured record per identified building, with
 212 fields such as site, building, order, typology, building type, evidence for style, date,
 213 age and evidence for date. Any fields where information is not extracted from the document
 214 is imputed with a NULL value.

215 **Results.** Based on the filtered records above, we compiled 2,654 distinct building entries with
 216 structured metadata and evidence. These structured information support aggregation across
 217 documents and enable downstream analysis of stylistic distribution, chronological trends, and
 218 site specific comparisons. An example is shown in Table 7.

Table 7 – Example structured metadata entry.

Field	Value
doc id	jstor-4238755
doc url	https://www.jstor.org/stable/4238755
site	Agrigento
building	Temple of Herakles
order	Doric
typology	Peripteral
building type	Temple
evidence for style	“In mainland Greece; peripteral Doric temples typically have a pronaos, cella, and opisthodomos, and sometimes an adyton at the rear.” “The temple of Herakles at built ca. 500 B.C., is apparently the earliest in Sicily to include stone stairs (fig. 1).”
date	ca. 500 BCE
age	Archaic
evidence for date	“The temple of Herakles at built ca. 500 B.C., is apparently the earliest in Sicily to include stone stairs (fig. 1).”

219 5. Interactive Visualization of Processed Building and Site Metadata

220 Starting from the 2,654 building level records compiled in the previous steps, we resolved
 221 site identifiers and geographic coordinates by matching and joining entity names with coordinate
 222 data from [vici.org](https://www.vici.org) and [wikipedia.org](https://www.wikipedia.org). For sites and buildings that did not match either source,
 223 we queried ChatGPT for coordinates; entries derived in this way were flagged with a Boolean
 224 `less_certain` indicator and are rendered with a lighter marker color in the interactive map to
 225 signal lower confidence. We then aggregated buildings by site, storing a single display coordinate
 226 per site together with a compact summary of extracted attributes.

227 An interactive map was implemented in React with Mapbox². Each site appears as a single
 228 marker, and selecting a marker opens a side panel that lists the buildings at that site together
 229 with the extracted attributes, including order, typology, building type, date, and age, and it shows
 230 the associated evidence text. Filters for order, typology, and age operate at map scope so that
 231 both visible markers and the side panel update in concert. To improve readability at small scales,

²<https://docs.mapbox.com/help/tutorials/use-mapbox-gl-js-with-react/>

232 markers cluster dynamically and expand as the user zooms in. Basic search by site or building
233 name and provenance links back to the source record support navigation and audit.

234 **Results.** The interactive map is available at <https://kharasso.github.io/classical-map/>

235 **6. Limitations and future direction**

236 Despite the limitations and the need to expand this map so that it represents all sites accu-
237 rately and equitably, it's major achievement is the fact that it can correlate buildings based on
238 certain criteria and at the same time give access to the bibliography that supports this correlation
239 in an automated way. This is the first step towards our ultimate goal to visualize the underlying
240 design principles of these buildings with spatial rules, which can then assist in the automated
241 generation of architectural reconstructions of fragmentary remains.

242 The explosion of generative AI tools that enable anyone to create surreal and seemingly
243 realistic visualizations of cultural heritage has intensified the question of their adherence to the
244 principles of intellectual and technical rigor established by the London Charter. Most of these
245 off-the-shelf tools generate text and images via opaque processes that cannot be verified and
246 hence fail to conform to the guidelines of the Charter of London. Our work tackles this problem
247 by developing novel machine learning methods to analyze and identify interpretable patterns in
248 the large body of archaeological record from the Greco-Roman architecture.

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257 **Conflict of interest disclosure**

258 **Data, script, code, and supplementary information availability**

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